

DATA-RICH CHARACTERISATION OF DAMAGE PROPOGATION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS AFTER INTERMEDIATE STRAIN RATE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

A novel semi-automated triggering methodology for the capture of high resolution white-light and infra-red (IR) images during a fatigue test is described, allowing digital image correlation (DIC) and thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA) to be applied without pausing of the cyclic load. The combined methodology is applied to crossply carbon-epoxy specimens, identifying various damage types including; transverse cracking, delaminations and longitudinal splitting, which was verified using X-ray computed tomography (CT).

1 INTRODUCTION

An experimental methodology that combines the DIC and TSA techniques for the identification of damage propagation in fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) material under cyclic loading is developed. The use of the two techniques allows the collection of surface strain and stress sum data, with the possibility of defining a new damage parameter. Unlike point measurement methods, the full-field techniques allow damage to be identified across an entire surface without prior knowledge of the material behaviour. The methodology builds upon previous work which enables the application of intermediate strain rate tensile loading to FRP specimens, imparting damage without complete specimen failure [1, 2]. The effect of high strain rate loading on subsequent damage propagation behaviour can therefore be studied.

The TSA technique relies on an infra-red (IR) sensor to record small changes in surface temperature which occur due to an applied stress, known as the thermoelastic effect. The relationship between the small temperature change, ΔT , and the surface temperature T_0 for orthotropic materials is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta T}{T_0} = K_1 \Delta \sigma_1 + K_2 \Delta \sigma_2 \quad (1)$$

where $K_1 = \frac{\alpha_1}{\rho C_p}$, $K_2 = \frac{\alpha_2}{\rho C_p}$

where α is the coefficient of thermal expansion, C_p is the specific heat at constant pressure and $\Delta \sigma$ is the change in stress and the subscripts 1,2 indicate the principal material/laminate coordinates.

Expressing the thermoelastic response in the form $\Delta T/T_0$ is useful as it makes account of any changes due to specimen heating at local damage sites [3, 4]. TSA is especially suited to the study of damage propagation as sinusoidal loading is required; hence data can be captured without the interruption of a fatigue cycle. A series of thermal images are recorded synchronously with the applied load signal across multiple loading cycles. The current work uses a CEDIP Silver 480M detector which features a lock-in amplifier to obtain ΔT . The Altair-Li 5.90 software by CEDIP is used to process IR images via to obtain plots of ΔT , T_0 and phase. In this case the phase is the angular difference between the applied stress and ΔT .

The DIC technique is performed on a set of pre-recorded digital images by tracking discrete areas of an image, known as cells. The surface under investigation requires a contrast pattern to allow the correlation algorithm to successfully track the surface deformation. A detailed description of the DIC technique is given in e.g. [5, 6, 7]. In the current work, DaVis 8.1.3 by LaVision was used for all correlations. To compute the subset displacement to greater accuracy, grey levels values are evaluated at subpixel locations using an interpolation method and the LSM method repeated in an iterative manner [8]. A 6th order spline method was used for greater accuracy at the cost of greater computation time.

2 AUTOMATED IMAGE CAPTURE METHODOLOGY

In TSA, equation (1) is only valid when adiabatic conditions prevail. This usually requires the application of a cyclic load above 10 Hz. The CEDIP Silver 480M camera is capable of imaging full-frame (320 x 128 pixels) at a frequency of 383 Hz, more than sufficient for sampling at this loading frequency. Capturing white-light images with a high resolution low-frame rate camera during fatigue loading requires considerably more effort. The use of high speed white-light cameras to collect a series of images throughout a loading cycle was considered but the spatial resolution of images and hence the quality of DIC data would be lower. Since high spatial resolution cameras generally have a low frame rate, accurate image timing is necessary to capture images at exactly the peak load in a cycle. A further benefit of using a methodology based around low-frame rate CCD cameras rather than high speed cameras is the decreased cost, allowing the methodology developed to be more accessible to future users.

A camera triggering and data collection system was developed in LabView 9.0 around a National Instruments USB-6211 data acquisition input/output device. This system allows the automatic and repeated capture of IR and white-light image data sets on specific intervals in a fatigue cycle. The Silver 480M IR camera was positioned nominally perpendicular to the specimen surface whilst being flanked by a set of two Manta G-504B 5 MPixel white-light cameras manufactured by Allied Vision Technologies. An overview of the Manta camera specifications is presented in Table 1.

Camera Model	Pixel Size	Sensor Type	Image Size	ADC	Max frame rate	Exposure range
Manta G-504B	3.45 x 3.45 μm	SONY IT CCD ICX655AL/AQ with microlenses	2452 x 2056 pixels	14 bit	9 Hz	38 μs to 60 s

Table 1: Overview of Allied Vision Technologies Manta G-504B camera specifications [9]

An Instron 8802 servo-hydraulic test machine operating in load control was used to apply a fatigue load to FRP specimens. Load control operation allows the load range and mean load to remain nominally constant throughout, regardless of damage onset in the FRP specimen. The machine was set to operate with amplitude control off, thus ensuring maximum accuracy in the frequency of applied loading. Loading cycles were counted in LabView using one of the analogue inputs of the USB-6211 device, smoothed and when a change in gradient is detected a loading cycle is recorded. When the number of loading cycles reaches a requested sampling point, the IR camera was triggered by 5V TTL pulse to begin the recording of an IR video for later TSA analysis. Next, the code triggers the stereo set of Manta cameras. A simple zero-crossing detector circuit was developed to aid the triggering of the Manta cameras to ensure high timing accuracy to within 0.77 ms of the point of maximum load. The circuit produces square pulses whenever the test machine load signal rises above 0 V. By specifying a fixed delay after receipt of the pulse, a set of stereo images are consistently captured at the point of maximum load. It should be noted that short exposure times are still required to minimise image blurring. As a consequence, a high intensity light emitting diode (LED) lighting system was developed using an array of 8 Intelligent LED Solutions ILH-ON01-ULWH-SC201 LED modules. Each LED module, outputting approximately 250 lumens, is combined with an acrylic lens of a full-width half maximum angle of 4.5° giving a concentrated column of visible light directed on the FRP specimen, with minimal IR output when compared to halogen-type illumination.

3 TEST SPECIMENS AND SURFACE PREPARATION

All test specimens used in the current work are of a symmetrical crossply lay-up with an outer 90° lamina, minimising any complicating effects from elastic coupling and promoting early surface damage in the form of transverse cracking. The damage behaviour of crossply material has been extensively documented, helping to simplify the interpretation of optical measurements. Four layers of Gurit SE84LV unidirectional carbon epoxy pre-preg material were used to give a $[90,0]_s$ lay-up and a panel thickness of 1.13 mm. Specimens were produced from the panels of 20 mm nominal width and 100 mm nominal gauge length. Specimens were coated in two passes of RS matt black paint followed by a light coat of Ambersil matt white paint to create a speckle pattern suitable for DIC analysis. A specimen prepared in a similar manner and examined under an optical microscope was found to have a paint coating thickness varying between 15 and 40 μm . The large variation of paint thickness is due to the high surface roughness of the material; an artefact of the peel-ply fabric required during manufacture. No difference in IR response could be noted as a result of the speckle pattern.

4 IR DATA COLLECTION

To check for adiabatic conditions, a CFRP specimen was cyclically loaded at 109 ± 87.7 MPa over a range of frequencies. The specimen was imaged using the IR camera, processed using TSA and the ΔT data averaged over the entire specimen area. The thermoelastic response across various loading frequencies is plotted in Figure 1. The CFRP specimen tends towards a ΔT value of 0.162 °C at frequencies above approximately 4 Hz, signifying adiabatic conditions. Based on these trials, cyclic loads were kept at or above 5 Hz for all tests subsequently conducted.

Figure 1: Effect of loading frequency on the thermoelastic response of speckle patterned CFRP

A consequence of applying strain to a material is that any given area on the material surface will undergo rigid body motion. Rigid body motion during the recording of an IR video is detrimental to TSA analysis as the incident IR radiation of individual pixels becomes a combination of the original sampling area and surrounding areas. Motion compensation was performed using the 'Random Motion' 5.90 software by CEDIP. As the quality of the motion compensation procedure is highly dependent on the sharpness of the tracking points used, the most suitable method for producing tracking marks was investigated. Low emissivity aluminium foil markings gave the highest IR contrast and the most stable video after motion compensation and was therefore used for all tests. The self-adhesive aluminium foil was found to remain well adhered to the specimen surface even after the application of in excess of one million loading cycles.

A known limitation the triggering methodology is the timing of the IR video. The IR camera begins recording at an arbitrary time and hence can start at any point within a loading cycle. As the motion compensation is applied with reference to the first image in the video sequence, any two motion compensated IR videos are likely to be with reference to different starting load values. For this

reason, all IR videos collected were cropped to start at the image closest to the first maximum load point by study of the load cell voltage recorded with IR images.

5 DAMAGE PROPAGATION IN CROSSPLY CFRP SPECIMENS

Previously undamaged CFRP specimens were cyclically loaded under tension-tension loading in an Instron 8802 servo-hydraulic test machine operating in load control, further details are given in Table 2. The specimens were undamaged prior to application of cyclic load. Surface damage was expected to occur rapidly during the initial stages of fatigue life; hence data collection intervals were shorter during the initial 10000 cycles. A summary of camera settings is presented in Table 3.

Specimen	Mean Stress	Cyclic Stress Amplitude	Frequency	Loading Cycles	Data collection intervals	
					< 10000 cycles	> 10000 cycles
[90,0] _s CFRP	300 MPa	270 MPa	5 Hz	250000	Every 500 cycles	Every 5000 cycles

Table 2: Test summary for previously undamaged CFRP specimens

Camera	Image size (pixels)	Imaging area on specimen (mm)	Spatial resolution (mm/pixel)	Imaging frequency (Hz)	Images captured	Exposure/integration time (μ s)
2 x AVT Manta G-504B	2452 x 2056	19.96 x 28.92	0.014	N/A	1 at min load 1 at max load	900
1 x CEDIP Silver 480M	320 x 256	19.96 x 67.23	0.261	383	600	1300

Table 3: Camera settings for tests conducted on undamaged CFRP specimens

Prior to each test, two sets of white light images were taken of the specimen at zero load to provide reference images for DIC analysis. In addition to the motion compensation markers, a piece of aluminium foil was also attached to the centre of the specimen and IR and white-light images taken, allowing the two datasets to be aligned during post processing. The foil was then removed prior to the test.

White-light images were processed in DaVis 8.1 using a cell size of 31 x 31 pixels, a step size of 6 pixels and a 6th order spline subpixel interpolation method. IR videos were motion compensated using the procedure previously described and TSA processed using Altair LI 5.90. A Matlab code was developed to enable DIC and TSA data to be overlaid. The code uses the DIC vertical and horizontal displacement vectors to shift the DIC strain data to their correct spatial location for each image. Using the foil markers as a point of reference, the IR data is spatially interpolated to match the DIC data points, so allowing TSA and DIC data to be overlaid. Maps of longitudinal (ϵ_{yy}), horizontal (ϵ_{xx}) and shear strain (ϵ_{xy}) were calculated using DIC. Maps of thermoelastic temperature change (ΔT), mean temperature (T_0) and phase were also obtained. ΔT data was divided by the mean temperature T_0 at each pixel location to give a normalised thermoelastic response ($\Delta T/T_0$) as per equation 1. The thermoelastic constants K_1 and K_2 were not evaluated. Selected data sets from all data types are presented in Figure 2. The normalised thermoelastic response ($\Delta T/T_0$) and longitudinal strain maps (ϵ_{yy}) from the first, second and sixth data sets collected are shown at higher magnification in Figure 3. Despite the first data set being collected after just 10 loading cycles, significant damage has already occurred to the surface 90° layer. Multiple horizontal lines of high strain, evident in the longitudinal strain map, were found to match spatially with horizontal lines of reduced thermoelastic response. Such behaviour is expected as DIC records the crack opening displacement as an increase in longitudinal strain whilst TSA measures a decreased thermoelastic response as the cracked surface layer has a reduced load-bearing capability. Most cracks were found to form across the entire specimen width within the 500 loading cycles between data collection intervals. Some examples of slowly propagating transverse cracks were found, one of which is highlighted inside the boxes shown in Figure 3. Between 500 and 3000 cycles a crack initiates from the left edge, whilst a pre-existing crack propagates by approximately 1.8 mm. In subsequent images the two cracks are shown to coalesce.

Figure 2: Full-field data collected during the fatigue loading of a previously undamaged crossply CFRP specimen

Transverse crack saturation is reached at around 6000 cycles. After which, a region of low thermoelastic response can be noted to form at the bottom of the data map at the right specimen edge. Between 6000 and 9500 cycles this region spreads upwards. Between 14500 and 19500 cycles a similar behaviour can be noted at the left specimen edge. The TSA phase and DIC shear strain (ϵ_{xy}) maps were studied for further information on this behaviour. Under adiabatic conditions the phase map will display either 0° or 180° , indicating areas of compression or tension. Non-adiabatic conditions, such as at locations of damage cause a shift in the phase angle of the IR signal relative to the applied loading. In FRP specimens, frictional heating between damaged layers or crack surfaces takes a finite time to conduct to the surface, causing a phase change in the recorded IR signal.

Figure 3: Development of longitudinal strain (ϵ_{yy}) and normalised thermoelastic response ($\Delta T/T_0$) during the early fatigue life of a previously undamaged crossply CFRP specimen.

Whilst some undamaged patches of material remain at 0° phase at 6500 cycles, the majority of the specimen surface is out of phase, indicating widespread surface damage. From 6500 cycles onwards, a change in the response occurs. Between 6000 and 9500 cycles, an area of negative phase propagates vertically from the bottom of the image at the right edge of the specimen. This behaviour coincides with regions of high shear strain shown in the DIC data. Between 14500 and 19500 cycles a similar response occurs at the left specimen edge. The change in response is consistent with

delaminations propagating from the free edge of the specimen, which is a dominant failure mode in cross ply laminates caused by the free edge effect. CT scanning was conducted on the specimen, which validated the damage modes identified.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A methodology for the semi-automated collection of white-light and IR images for the study of FRP specimens during un-interrupted fatigue tests has been presented. The approach has used simple electronics, intense LED lighting and a LabView based methodology to achieve accurate camera timing, so allowing the use of low frequency, high resolution white light cameras during cyclic loading. The use of high resolution cameras has subsequently given high spatial resolution strain maps, allowing the imaging of small scale damage in CFRP specimens.

The use of a combined TSA and DIC methodology has allowed various damage types to be identified in the two types of specimen tested, including surface and subsurface damage types. Transverse cracking in CFRP laminates has been clearly identified in longitudinal strain and normalised thermoelastic data, whilst delaminations have been identified in shear strain and TSA phase data. The damage behaviour of the CFRP specimen has been successfully validated using CT analysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Battams, "The Use of Optical Techniques to Assess the Damage Tolerance of Composite Materials," Doctoral Thesis, Faculty of Engineering and the Environment, University of Southampton, 2014.
- [2] G. Battams, J. Dulieu-Barton and S. Boyd, Data-Rich Characterisation of Damage in Composite Materials During Intermediate Strain Rate Loading, *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Composites Testing and Model Identification (CompTest 2015)* (Eds. C. González, C. López, J. LLorca), Madrid, Spain, April 8-10, 2015, University Press, Porto, Paper 41, 2006, pp. 174-175.
- [3] J. Dulieu-Barton and P. Stanley, "Development and applications of thermoelastic stress analysis," *The Journal of Strain Analysis for Engineering Design*, **33**, 1998 pp.
- [4] D. A. Crump, "Reducing the Cost of Manufacturing Composite Aircraft Secondary Structure," Doctoral Thesis, University of Southampton, 2009.
- [5] M. A. Sutton, J.-J. Orteu, and H. W. Schreier, *Image Correlation for Shape, Motion and Deformation Measurements*, Springer US, 2009.
- [6] B. Pan, K. Qian, H. Xie, and A. Asundi, "Two-dimensional digital image correlation for in-plane displacement and strain measurement: a review," *Measurement Science and Technology*, **20**, 2009.
- [7] B. Pan, "Recent Progress in Digital Image Correlation," *Experimental Mechanics*, **51**, pp. 1223-1235, 2011.
- [8] P. Lava, S. Cooreman, S. Coppeters, M. De Strycker, and D. Debruyne, "Assessment of measuring errors in DIC using deformation fields generated by plastic FEA," *Optics and Lasers in Engineering*, **47**, pp. 747-753, 2009.
- [9] Technical Manual - AVT GigE Vision Cameras V7.0.1, A. V. Technologies, 2013.